

ISic4371

I.Sicily inscription 4371

Language

Latin

Type

Honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Seen by Campagna 2005

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 48 cm

Width 32 cm

Depth 0.2 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 90 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to
2
: mm

Text

1. Domit[iae Cn. f.]
2. [--]Imp. Do[mitiani]
3. [--]Cae[saris (uxori)]

Apparatus

Text from Manganaro 1964 and photo

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1964. Iscrizioni latine e greche dal nuovo edificio termale di

Taormina. *Cronache di archeologia e di storia dell'arte*. 3: 38-68. At 41 no.4
tav.XVI.2

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